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Amphizoidae: Amphizoa

Carabidae: *Arthropterus*

Claval line and CuP are reduced

Carabidae: *Calosoma schrayeri*

Carabidae: *Calosoma* sp.

Carabidae: *Megacephala*

Carabidae: *Omophron americanum*

Carabidae: *Pheropsophus verticalis*

Dytiscidae: *Hyderodes schuckardi*

Macrogyrus sp.

Gyrinidae: *Macrogyrus*

New Guinea

Note well retained basal pattern of the radial and medial branching

Adephaga: Gyrinidae: *Macrogyrus*

Coleoptera apomorphies in hind wing articulation:

AX-PC & C (tegula) reduced; B-R partly membranized; F-M subdivided; B-M large, connected with B-Cu; AX-Cu (3Ax) small, sutured, and often fragmented; AX-Cu fused with F-Cu; F-Cu fused with FA

Gyrinidae: *Macrogyrus*

N. Guinea

7.2mm

New Guinea Gyrinidae: *Macrogyrus*

VENTRAL VIEW

WING
LIFTED

Gyrinidae: *Macrogyrus*

Gyrinidae: *Spanglerogyrus aldiventris*

Haliplidae: *Halipus*

Hygrobiidae: *Hygrobia nigra*

11 mm

Hygrobiidae: *Hygrobia nigra*

Noteridae: *Hydrocanthus australasiae*

Shows reduced claval line; MA reaches posterior wing margin!

Rhysodidae: *Omoglymmius hammatus*

close to: Noleridae

Wing articulation close to Macrogyrus. cannot be derived from Cerauridae!

5.2 mm

Trachypachidae: *Trachypachus gibbsi*

Shows subdivision of medial basivenale (B-M) and MA joining R and RP

Trachypachidae: *Trachypachus gibbsi*

Indicates very well the basal coleopteran veinal pattern! But CuP and claval line are completely reduced. Anal lobe clearly starts at the anal fold, while AA 3+4 joined remigium